

Probing Maximally Divergent Conceptual Regions in Large Language Models Through Prompt Engineering

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Abstract: Large Language Models (LLMs) have shown impressive capabilities in natural language understanding and reasoning; however, their internal conceptual organization remains largely opaque. This study introduces a novel prompt engineering approach to explore the latent conceptual spaces of LLMs by identifying maximally divergent conceptual regions. It draws on the conceptual spaces framework, in which knowledge is represented as geometric regions defined by quality dimensions. Within this framework, a proxy metric referred to as the conceptual divergence count is proposed. This metric represents the number of maximally divergent conceptual regions identified through structured prompts. Although the metric does not measure dimensionality in the geometric or architectural sense, it serves as an indicator of a model's conceptual diversity. The method is applied to a range of LLMs, including models from the Gemini, GPT, and Claude families, as well as additional models such as Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct, Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3, Gemma-3-12B-IT, and Grok-3. The results show substantial variation in diversity, with gemini-2.5-flash-preview-05-20 achieving the highest value of 91 and claude-3-7-sonnet-20250219 recording the lowest value of 7. These findings suggest that diversity, as measured by this method, may provide insights into the internal organization of conceptual representations. While the metric is to be an indicator of a model's factual knowledge structure, providing complementary insight into its internal organization, it does not directly measure knowledge accuracy. The proposed approach contributes a geometric perspective to the evaluation of LLM knowledge, complementing existing benchmarks and supporting interpretability.

Keywords: conceptual spaces, prompt engineering, knowledge representation, interpretability, conceptual regions, maximally divergent, factual knowledge capacity

Categories: I.2, I.1.2, I.2.7, I.2.4, H.1, H.3, H.4, E.0

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1 Introduction

Large Language Models (LLMs) are now widely used in various natural language processing tasks, demonstrating exceptional capabilities in reasoning, knowledge retrieval, and language understanding. Despite these advances, the internal organization of knowledge and concepts within such models remains insufficiently understood. This lack of clarity limits the ability to interpret, evaluate, and enhance their capacity for factual knowledge and reasoning performance.

The conceptual spaces framework, introduced by Gärdenfors [Gärdenfors, 04], provides a geometric approach to knowledge representation by modeling concepts as convex regions within a multidimensional space defined by quality dimensions. This framework bridges symbolic and subsymbolic representations, enabling

mathematically grounded reasoning about similarity, prototypes, and conceptual relations.

In this study, the conceptual spaces perspective is applied to examine how fundamental concepts are internally represented by LLMs. A prompt engineering-based method is introduced to identify maximally divergent conceptual regions within an LLM's latent conceptual space. By determining the maximum number of such regions, a diversity metric is established to approximate the richness and structural organization of the factual knowledge encoded in these models.

The present approach contributes to ongoing research on the interpretability and evaluation of the internal knowledge structures of LLMs. It provides empirical measurements for models especially from the Gemini, GPT, and Claude families, revealing notable variations in conceptual diversity. These differences may reflect variations in architecture, training methodology, and representational capacity.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides a review of theoretical foundations and previous studies on conceptual spaces, prompt engineering, and the evaluation of LLMs. Section 3 describes the proposed method for identifying maximally divergent conceptual regions, including its geometric motivation and prompt design. Section 4 presents the experimental setup and results, highlighting diversity measurements especially across different LLM families. Section 5 discusses the implications, limitations, and potential extensions of the approach. Section 6 presents the conclusion of the paper and describes possible avenues for future research.

2 Related Work

The conceptual spaces framework, introduced by Gärdenfors [Gärdenfors, 04], offers a geometric perspective on knowledge representation in which concepts are modeled as convex regions within multidimensional spaces defined by quality dimensions such as color, shape, or taste. This perspective connects symbolic and subsymbolic representations, enabling mathematically grounded reasoning about similarity, prototypes, and conceptual relations. It provides a formal structure for understanding how conceptual meaning can be embedded in geometric form, making it a valuable foundation for examining the internal organization of knowledge in artificial intelligence systems.

Building on this foundation, recent work by Kumar et al. [Kumar, 24] applies the conceptual spaces approach to the context of LLMs, investigating how entities can be represented and ranked along conceptual space dimensions. Their study assesses fine-tuning strategies for improving the ability of LLMs to model such spaces, comparing pointwise and pairwise ranking approaches and showing that the choice of method influences the quality of conceptual representation. To address challenges such as the scarcity of ground truth rankings for subjective and perceptual features, Kumar et al. use structured numerical attributes from resources such as Wikidata to enhance LLM modeling of conceptual dimensions.

These contributions provide the theoretical and methodological basis for adapting the conceptual spaces framework to probe the latent structures of LLMs through prompt engineering and to measure the diversity of conceptual regions.

The evaluation of LLMs has evolved into a multidimensional challenge that includes accuracy, reasoning, robustness, fairness, and domain-specific performance.

Chang et al. [Chang, 24] present a comprehensive survey of LLM evaluation approaches, categorizing methods into automatic and human assessments and highlighting critical issues such as metric reliability, ethical considerations, and generalization capacity. Zhao et al. [Zhao, 23] provide a broader survey of LLM development, emphasizing the relationships among model scale, training data, and computational resources, and discussing the challenges of assessing emergent capabilities and internal knowledge structures. Ray [Ray, 23] examines ChatGPT in detail, outlining its architecture, applications, and limitations, with particular attention to the use of prompt engineering to improve evaluation relevance.

In addition to these surveys, several frameworks have been proposed to support systematic and transparent LLM evaluation. The Holistic Evaluation of Language Models (HELM) [Liang, 22] adopts a multi-metric approach across diverse use cases, emphasizing transparency and trade-off analysis between performance dimensions. Chiang et al. [Chiang, 24] present Chatbot Arena, an open platform for large-scale, human-preference-based evaluation through crowdsourced pairwise comparisons. Zheng et al. [Zheng, 23] extend this approach with the LLM-as-a-judge framework, showing that advanced LLMs can approximate human evaluations with high agreement rates. Kiela et al. [Kiela, 21] introduce Dynabench, a dynamic platform that enables continuous dataset updates through human and model interaction in adversarial data collection to reveal hidden weaknesses in LLMs. Building on these efforts, Çetin et al. [Çetin, 24] present an empirical assessment of five leading LLMs including ChatGPT 4, ChatGPT 3.5, Claude, Bard/Gemini, and Llama-2, applied to static code analysis for PHP vulnerability detection, offering quantitative evidence on their detection performance and false positive rates. While these frameworks have greatly improved the transparency and comprehensiveness of LLM evaluation, they mainly focus on external task performance and user preference rather than exploring the internal conceptual organization of the models. This limitation highlights the need for complementary approaches, such as the conceptual space method proposed in this study, which examines diversity and structure within the models' latent knowledge representations.

Task-oriented benchmarks have been central to LLM evaluation. The General Language Understanding Evaluation (GLUE) benchmark [Wang, 18] established a multi-task framework for assessing a wide range of linguistic capabilities. This was followed by SuperGLUE [Wang, 19], which addressed GLUE's ceiling effects by introducing more challenging tasks. Srivastava et al. [Srivastava, 22] expanded the evaluation scope with BIG-bench, a large-scale benchmark containing more than 200 tasks designed to probe both quantitative performance and emergent qualitative abilities. The Chain-of-Thought Hub (CoT Hub) [Fu, 23] focuses specifically on reasoning evaluation, aggregating results from multiple reasoning-intensive benchmarks and highlighting the role of structured prompting in eliciting complex reasoning capabilities. These surveys, frameworks, and benchmarks provide the methodological groundwork for the proposed prompt engineering approach to exploring conceptual spaces. They illustrate the transition of LLM evaluation from static, task-oriented metrics to more adaptive and comprehensive methodologies. Nevertheless, most of these approaches continue to concentrate on external model performance, offering limited insight into the internal structure of knowledge representation. Building on this foundation, the present study advances evaluation

efforts by incorporating a geometric perspective that investigates conceptual diversity and the organization of latent knowledge within LLMs.

Zhuang et al. [Zhuang, 23] introduced an adaptive testing framework based on the principles of Computerized Adaptive Testing in psychometrics to efficiently evaluate the cognitive abilities of LLMs. Their method adjusts the difficulty of test items in real time according to model performance, allowing accurate estimation of abilities with fewer questions and enabling direct comparisons between LLMs and humans. By applying Item Response Theory (IRT) to model latent traits, they generated detailed diagnostic reports covering domains such as subject knowledge, mathematical reasoning, and programming. Although their study focuses on adaptive psychometric evaluation of cognitive ability, the present research takes a complementary direction by exploring the diversity of conceptual spaces through the identification of maximally divergent conceptual regions using prompt-based techniques.

An important dimension of LLM evaluation concerns cognitive and reasoning abilities, which include logical coherence, compositionality, abstraction, and adaptability to novel tasks. Lee et al. [Lee, 24] investigate reasoning using the Abstraction and Reasoning Corpus (ARC), employing the Language of Thought framework to evaluate logical coherence, compositionality, and productivity. They find that although LLMs perform well in simple pattern recognition, they often fail to produce novel solutions under abstract constraints. Liu et al. [Liu, 23] evaluate logical reasoning capabilities with benchmarks such as LogiQA, ReClor, and AR-LSAT, observing strong results on familiar datasets but a marked drop in performance on out-of-distribution tasks. Xu et al. [Xu, 25] extend this analysis with a fine-grained reasoning framework covering deductive, inductive, abductive, and mixed-form reasoning, and identify recurring error patterns related to evidence selection and completeness of explanations. Gendron et al. [Gendron, 23] emphasize further limitations in abstract reasoning, showing that advanced prompting strategies often fail to bridge the gap between surface-level pattern recognition and genuine abstraction.

Robustness in reasoning is also studied in counterfactual and adversarial contexts. Wu et al. [Wu, 24] explore counterfactual reasoning and report that performance declines sharply when tasks deviate from the training distribution. Ni et al. [Ni, 24] examine a different cognitive domain, social cognition, by assessing Theory of Mind (ToM) and social learning abilities through gamified evaluations. Their findings highlight the difficulty LLMs face in integrating others' beliefs with actions that are appropriate for the context.

Beyond general reasoning, research has examined specialized cognitive capabilities. Wu and Guo [Wu, 25] evaluate LLM spatial cognition by testing topological, directional, and distance reasoning, showing that prompt design has a significant effect on spatial reasoning accuracy. Riccardi et al. [Riccardi, 24] investigate semantic boundaries through the Two Word Test (TWT), a benchmark that measures LLMs' ability to distinguish between meaningful and nonsensical noun–noun combinations, a task that is effortless for humans but challenging for current models. These studies expose both the range and the vulnerability of LLM reasoning abilities, emphasizing the importance of alternative probing approaches such as the proposed conceptual space diversity analysis, which seeks to capture structural reasoning potential beyond conventional benchmarks. Traditional evaluation methods primarily assess task accuracy and surface-level performance, offering limited insight into the internal representation and organization of concepts within a model's latent space. The

proposed analysis addresses this limitation by investigating the geometric structure and diversity of conceptual regions, providing a more intrinsic understanding of reasoning capacity. This perspective shifts the focus from external performance measures to the internal conceptual architecture that underlies reasoning in LLMs.

Understanding how LLMs internally represent and organize knowledge is central to interpretability research as well as the development of effective evaluation methods. Zhao et al. [Zhao, 24] present a comprehensive survey of interpretability techniques, covering both fine-tuning and prompting paradigms, and categorizing methods into local and global approaches such as feature attribution, attention visualization, and concept-based analyses. At the architectural level, the Transformer model introduced by Vaswani et al. [Vaswani, 17] forms the basis of modern LLMs. Its self-attention mechanisms enable the modeling of long-range dependencies and hierarchical structures, which directly influence the formation of latent conceptual spaces.

Several studies have investigated LLMs' factual and conceptual representations. Petroni et al. [Petroni, 19] introduced the LAMA probe, showing that pretrained language models can retrieve factual and commonsense knowledge through cloze-style queries, often matching or surpassing traditional knowledge extraction systems without fine-tuning. However, later studies have identified limitations in these probing techniques. Cao et al. [Cao, 21] demonstrate that the performance of masked language models can be artificially inflated by prompt biases, type guidance, and contextual leakage rather than by genuine conceptual knowledge. Vulić et al. [Vulić, 20] explore the distribution of lexical semantic knowledge in models such as BERT and RoBERTa, finding that type-level lexical knowledge is concentrated in lower layers and dispersed across parameters, with extraction strategies having a substantial effect on representational quality. Pezeshkpour [Pezeshkpour, 23] adopts an information-theoretic perspective, using entropy and KL-divergence to measure changes in factual knowledge before and after knowledge instillation, and identifies conditions in which prompt-based methods underperform.

Complementary approaches evaluate the calibration and self-awareness of the knowledge held by LLMs. Kadavath et al. [Kadavath, 22] introduce probabilistic measures such as $P(\text{True})$ and $P(\text{IK})$ to quantify correctness confidence and self-knowledge, showing that larger models exhibit improved calibration and better generalization across domains. AlKhamissi et al. [AlKhamissi, 22] review the use of LLMs as knowledge bases, outlining challenges related to access, consistency, editability, reasoning, and explainability, and surveying strategies including probing, prompting, and model editing. These studies highlight the complexity of interpreting LLM knowledge structures and motivate the adaptation of the conceptual spaces framework to probe these structures through prompt engineering, with a focus on the diversity of maximally divergent conceptual regions.

Robustness and factual reliability are essential in the evaluation of LLMs because even models with strong reasoning and knowledge representation capabilities can generate misleading or incorrect outputs under certain conditions. Rawte et al. [Rawte, 23] present a broad taxonomy of hallucinations in large foundation models, categorizing them into types arising from knowledge gaps, biases, and misunderstandings, and reviewing detection and mitigation strategies across multiple modalities. Zhang et al. [Zhang, 23] refine this classification for LLMs, distinguishing between hallucinations that arise from inconsistencies with the input, those that result from conflicts within the surrounding context, and those that contradict established

facts, and emphasizing the particular risks posed by fact-based errors in real-world deployment.

In addition to internal biases and knowledge gaps, the formulation of prompts plays a significant role in model reliability. Zhu et al. [Zhu, 23] address this issue by introducing PromptRobust, a benchmark designed to evaluate LLM robustness against adversarial prompt perturbations, including typographical errors, synonym substitutions, and semantic shifts. Their findings show that small variations in prompt structure can disproportionately affect model outputs, revealing vulnerabilities in prompt-driven evaluation settings. The prompting behaviors of undergraduate students are analyzed [Sawalha, 24], and it is observed that reformulated and multi-question prompts yield considerably higher ChatGPT response accuracy than direct copy-and-paste inputs. It is also shown that prompt formulation and refinement strongly influence LLM output quality, highlighting the importance of prompt-engineering literacy within educational contexts. Knoth et al. [Knoth, 24] highlight the crucial link between AI literacy and effective prompt formulation, noting that the quality of LLM outputs largely depends on users' grasp of prompt design concepts. Their results demonstrate that advancing AI literacy enables users to craft more structured and purposeful prompts, which in turn improves the precision and consistency of model responses. Collectively, these studies demonstrate that even when LLMs exhibit strong conceptual or reasoning structures, external factors such as input variability and adversarial manipulation can undermine output quality. This reinforces the need for evaluation approaches, such as the proposed conceptual diversity probing, that assess internal representational capacity independently of surface-level prompt perturbations and provide a more stable foundation for understanding LLM reliability.

As LLMs continue to grow in size and computational demands, knowledge distillation and model compression have become essential for improving efficiency while striving to preserve conceptual and reasoning capabilities. Yang et al. [Yang, 24] provide a comprehensive survey of distillation methods for LLMs, covering both white box approaches such as distillation based on logits, distillation using hints, and transfer of intermediate representations, as well as black box approaches such as contextual learning, reasoning chain transfer, and instruction-following distillation. Their analysis emphasizes the challenge of ensuring that student models retain the conceptual structures and generalization abilities of larger teacher models, particularly across diverse tasks and robustness benchmarks.

Schellaert et al. [Schellaert, 25] present a complementary approach by introducing assessor models that predict LLM performance at the individual instance level. By fine-tuning models such as DeBERTa on the outputs of generative LLMs across varied benchmarks, they demonstrate that assessor models can outperform the models' own self-assessment in predicting success or failure. This meta-evaluation capability provides a potential tool for monitoring conceptual integrity during or after model compression. These studies underscore the difficulty of maintaining internal conceptual organization when reducing model size and highlight the value of probing methods such as the proposed diversity metric, which can help determine whether essential conceptual regions are preserved after compression.

Static benchmarks, although historically important, often suffer from dataset saturation and possible training-test contamination, leading to inflated performance estimates that may not accurately represent true generalization. Chen et al. [Chen, 25] address this problem by surveying advances in contamination-resistant evaluation,

advocating a shift from static to dynamic benchmarks, and proposing criteria such as correctness, scalability, diversity, and interpretability to guide benchmark development. Zhu et al. [Zhu, 2023] apply these principles in DYVAL, a dynamic evaluation framework that generates reasoning tasks on the fly using directed acyclic graph (DAG) structures. This approach enables fine-grained control over task complexity and uncovers limitations that static datasets may fail to reveal.

Other recent studies have focused on systematically increasing cognitive challenge and structural variety in dynamic benchmarks. Fan et al. [Fan, 23] introduced NPHardEval, which categorizes reasoning tasks according to computational complexity class, ranging from P to NP-hard, thereby enabling controlled evaluation across different levels of algorithmic difficulty. Lei et al. [Lei, 23] presented S3Eval, a synthetic, scalable, and systematic evaluation suite designed to assess reasoning and long-context capabilities through SQL execution tasks on randomly generated tables, with performance shown to correlate strongly with real-world benchmarks. Zhou et al. [Zhou, 22] presented Automatic Prompt Engineer (APE), a framework that conceptualizes prompt generation as a natural language program synthesis task. Utilizing LLMs in combination with black-box optimization, APE automatically generates and refines prompts to enhance model performance across a wide range of tasks, achieving human-level or superior results on benchmarks such as instruction induction, BIG-Bench, and chain-of-thought reasoning. While APE is primarily intended to enhance task performance, the present study uses prompt engineering to explore the diversity of conceptual regions within the conceptual spaces of LLMs, offering a geometric perspective for analyzing their internal knowledge structures. This approach moves beyond optimizing external outputs and instead focuses on uncovering how knowledge and concepts are internally organized and differentiated. By examining maximally divergent conceptual regions, the study provides insight into the representational richness and structural coherence of LLMs. In doing so, it complements performance-based evaluations with a more interpretive framework that clarifies how conceptual distinctions and relationships are encoded within these models.

These dynamic and adaptive evaluation approaches share the common goal of creating evolving, contamination-resistant benchmarks that more accurately reflect real-world variability and model adaptability. The proposed conceptual space probing method is aligned with this goal by introducing a dynamic, prompt-based approach for mapping the diversity of latent conceptual regions, thereby complementing these efforts with a geometric and structural perspective on LLM evaluation.

The conceptual and architectural foundations of modern LLMs can be traced to several pivotal contributions. Brown et al. [Brown, 20] introduced GPT-3, demonstrating that increasing the model size to 175 billion parameters substantially improves task-agnostic few-shot learning capabilities. Their work showed that large models can generalize to a wide range of tasks such as translation, question answering, and commonsense reasoning without requiring fine-tuning. Instead, these models leverage in-context learning through natural language prompts. This provided strong evidence that LLMs encode rich latent structures capable of flexible knowledge retrieval, a premise that supports this study's view of LLMs as conceptual spaces.

In contrast, Floridi and Chiriatti [Floridi, 20] presented a critical analysis of GPT-3, highlighting the gap between statistical fluency and genuine semantic understanding. Through mathematical, semantic, and ethical examinations, they argued that although

GPT-3 produces contextually appropriate text, it lacks deep comprehension and reasoning. This raises concerns about equating the quality of linguistic output with the depth of conceptual knowledge. The distinction between surface-level fluency and structural knowledge representation strengthens the motivation for the present approach, which investigates the diversity of maximally divergent conceptual regions in order to assess internal capacity beyond output plausibility.

Previous research has made notable progress in evaluating LLMs across dimensions such as reasoning, robustness, and interpretability. However, the majority of existing approaches continue to emphasize external task performance rather than exploring the internal organization of conceptual knowledge. Although benchmarking and dynamic evaluation frameworks have evolved considerably, the geometric configuration and diversity of conceptual regions within LLMs remain insufficiently explored. Gaining insight into these internal structures is crucial for understanding how models encode, relate, and differentiate conceptual entities beyond observable outputs. To address this gap, the present study builds upon the conceptual spaces framework and applies a prompt engineering approach to identify maximally divergent conceptual regions, offering a geometric lens through which the internal differentiation of knowledge representations can be examined. This perspective enhances interpretability by revealing the structural foundations of conceptual diversity and representational capacity, forming the theoretical and methodological groundwork for the proposed probing method and its empirical evaluation in the following sections.

3 The Proposed Method

Conceptual spaces were introduced in [Gardenfors, 04] as a framework for representing knowledge as geometric regions defined by meaningful dimensions. In this study, such a conceptual space is interpreted as one formed by LLMs, corresponding to regions in the models' internal embedding space. The dimensions of this space represent the diversity of the LLMs' internal embeddings, making it a high-dimensional vector space. To aid in understanding conceptual divergence, this high-dimensional space is described using the metaphor of a hypersphere. This metaphor is used in a loose and illustrative sense, without implying strict geometric properties such as equal distances or uniform distribution across the surface. Although the selected concepts are semantically different, their arrangement within the model's latent space is not directly observable and may not follow precise geometric rules regarding position or spacing. The hypersphere metaphor is employed solely to convey the notion of maximal conceptual spread, rather than actual geometric placement. The surface spread of this hypersphere, interpreted as the number of conceptually divergent regions it contains, serves as an indicator of the model's conceptual diversity, which may be related to its capacity for factual knowledge.

To make this idea more intuitive, a simplified two-dimensional analogy is presented in which the conceptual space is represented as a circle. A fundamental concept is placed at the center. The concept that is furthest from the center, both conceptually and spatially, is considered its opposite. A third concept is then selected to be as distant as possible from both of the first two concepts, thereby increasing divergence. This process is repeated, with each new concept chosen to be maximally distant from all previously identified concepts. Eventually, the process produces

repetitions or semantically similar concepts. The number of truly divergent concepts identified before this point of saturation is used as an estimate of the sphere’s capacity, and thus indirectly as an estimate of the amount of structured factual knowledge encoded in the LLM.

Figure 1: Geometric Analogy of Conceptual Divergence

Figure 1 conceptually illustrates the rationale of the proposed probing method. Each point represents a concept identified through prompt-based exploration within the model’s latent conceptual space. The progressive separation of points (C1–C8) depicts the iterative identification of increasingly distinct conceptual regions, beginning from a central, fundamental concept. This geometric analogy demonstrates how the method expands from a core region toward the conceptual boundary of the model, thereby approximating its representational capacity.

Figure 1 is a purely two-dimensional conceptual analogy created for illustrative purposes. In practice, an LLM operates in a high-dimensional, non-Euclidean space without direct access to geometric distances. In the case of a hypersphere, applying this method from an initial point within the space will, through successive iterations,

eventually identify points located on the surface of the hypersphere. At each step, the algorithm selects the point that maximizes the cumulative distance from all previously chosen points, thereby expanding the set of identified locations outward toward the boundary. From a geometric perspective, this process is mathematically valid because the criterion of maximal divergence ensures a progressive outward movement until the surface is reached. In the context of conceptual spaces, convergence to the surface metaphorically represents reaching the outer limits of the model's representational capacity. The resulting distribution of points can therefore serve as an empirical approximation of the hypersphere's conceptual boundary, providing insights into the maximal spread of distinct conceptual regions that the model can represent.

Figure 1 shows a geometric illustration of the first nine conceptually divergent points selected within a unit circle. This circle represents a simplified model of a conceptual space, similar to the latent knowledge space within an LLM. The process begins with the center of the circle, labeled C0, which represents a fundamental or central concept.

Each subsequent point, from C1 to C8, is selected iteratively according to a specific criterion. It must be the point within the circle that maximizes the total Euclidean distance from all previously chosen points. This greedy algorithm ensures that every new point diverges as much as possible from earlier concepts, thereby simulating the emergence of increasingly distinct conceptual regions. Figure 1 shows these points with different colored markers, each labeled accordingly (for example, C1 in blue, C2 in green, and up to C8 in brown). Dashed lines connect all pairs of points, illustrating the network of distance relationships that guides the selection process.

Figure 1 represents a geometric process of knowledge diversification. It illustrates how, even within a constrained space, an iterative selection procedure can reveal a sequence of maximally divergent conceptual regions. This method provides both a visual and mathematical analogy for assessing or exploring conceptual diversity in LLMs and related models of artificial cognition.

Using this method, the identified points align with the surface of the hypersphere, symbolizing maximally divergent conceptual directions. Therefore, the number of distinct concepts obtained through this process can be interpreted as an indicator of the LLM's capacity to represent factual knowledge. The implementation of this method through prompt engineering follows these steps:

1. Identify the fundamental concept

Prompt:

"What is the most important fundamental concept? Just return the concept."

The LLM's response is stored as <fundamental concept>.

2. Find the first maximally divergent concept

Prompt:

"What is the concept or compound concept that is most opposed to the following concepts: <fundamental concept>? If your response is a phrase or sentence, just return 'no'; if the response is a concept or compound concept, just return the response; otherwise, just return 'no'."

The <divergent concepts> set is initialized with both the <fundamental concept> and the first <divergent concept>.

3. Iteratively identify further maximally divergent concepts

Prompt:

"What is the concept or compound concept that is most opposed to the following concepts: <divergent concepts>? If your response is a phrase or sentence, just return 'no'; if the response is a concept or compound concept, just return the response; otherwise, just return 'no'."

Each newly identified <divergent concept> is added to the set and the process repeats until no further distinct concepts are found. The process ends upon reaching algorithmic saturation, which is defined as the point where no more than five identical responses occur across iterations. At this stage, further iterations produce only negligible changes in conceptual variation.

The prompts are carefully structured, concise, and semantically focused to generate concept-level outputs rather than descriptive or narrative responses. Each prompt follows a gradual refinement process, beginning with a fundamental concept query (for example, "What is the most important fundamental concept?") and progressing to contrastive prompts (for example, "What is the concept most opposed to the following concepts: ...?"). To maintain consistency and reproducibility, all prompts use a standardized syntax with clear instructions such as "Just return the concept" or "Return only the response." This controlled formulation reduces linguistic variability and allows the identification of distinct conceptual differences within the models' latent spaces. In addition, iterative prompt validation and normalization procedures are employed to eliminate ambiguous outputs, ensuring that each extracted concept represents a unique region in the conceptual space. Future researchers can apply comparable prompt engineering strategies, including progressive refinement, structural consistency, and controlled response scope, to reproduce and extend the present analysis.

4 Experimental Results

The diversity metric is interpreted as an indicator of a model's capacity to represent a broad range of distinct conceptual regions. Higher diversity scores indicate a richer distribution of conceptual representations, whereas lower scores suggest a more limited conceptual structure. This section examines these diversity values across different LLMs and compares them to evaluate representational breadth.

The evaluation of maximally divergent conceptual regions was conducted primarily for the Gemini, GPT, and Claude families and was extended to include four additional models, namely Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct, Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3, Gemma-3-12B-IT, and Grok-3, to broaden the comparative analysis. The proposed method was applied to each model, and the resulting dataset is reported in [Çulha, 25]. Algorithmic saturation was defined as the stage at which no more than five identical responses were obtained, indicating that further iterations contributed negligible conceptual variation.

Table 1 presents the diversity values calculated for the large language models included in this study. The table covers models from three major families, namely Gemini, GPT, and Claude, together with four additional individual models: Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct, Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3, Gemma-3-12B-IT, and Grok-3. The diversity value indicates the number of maximally divergent conceptual regions identified for each model through the applied prompt-based evaluation method. Among all examined

models, gemini-2.5-flash-preview-05-20 achieved the highest diversity score of 91, reflecting a greater conceptual capacity according to the proposed metric, while claude-3-7-sonnet-20250219 obtained the lowest score of 7. The results reveal substantial variation across both model families and individual models, suggesting notable differences in conceptual organization and factual knowledge representation.

Model Name	Diversity
gemini-1.5-flash-8b	11
gemini-1.5-flash	22
gemini-2.0-flash-lite	11
gemini-2.0-flash	14
gemini-2.5-flash-preview-05-20	91
gpt-3.5-turbo-0125	9
gpt-4-0613	18
gpt-4-turbo-2024-04-09	10
gpt-4o-2024-08-06	35
gpt-4.5-preview-2025-02-27	8
gpt-4.1-2025-04-14	12
claude-3-opus-20240229	10
claude-3-5-sonnet-20241022	10
claude-3-5-haiku-20241022	12
claude-3-7-sonnet-20250219	7
claude-sonnet-4-20250514	10
claude-opus-4-20250514	15
Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct	23
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	11
gemma-3-12b-it	42
grok-3	25

Table 1: Diversity of LLM Models

Figure 2 shows a transposed line plot that compares the diversity of the LLM families. The models are listed on the vertical axis from the highest to the lowest diversity value, and the horizontal axis shows the corresponding diversity values. Model families are identified by color, with Gemini in blue, GPT in green, and Claude in orange. The plot illustrates the variation in diversity both across and within model families.

Within the Gemini family, diversity values range from 11 to 91, with gemini-2.5-flash-preview-05-20 clearly surpassing earlier versions. The GPT family shows a narrower range, with no model exceeding a diversity value of 35. The Claude family has relatively consistent results between 7 and 15, indicating less variation in

representational diversity across its versions. Interestingly, some smaller models, such as gemini-1.5-flash, have diversity values higher than those of larger models from other families, suggesting that factors such as architecture and training methodology may influence diversity more than parameter count alone.

Figure 2: Diversity of Conceptual Regions Across LLM Families

Figure 3 illustrates the conceptual diversity scores summarized by model family, offering a comparative perspective on representational capacity across different LLM architectures. Each bar (or data point) denotes the mean diversity value for a family, with vertical lines or shaded regions representing the range observed among its variants. The Gemini models consistently appear at the upper end of the diversity spectrum, indicating a wider distribution of maximally divergent conceptual regions. GPT models exhibit moderate diversity values, while the Claude models cluster toward the lower range, suggesting a more compact conceptual organization. The mean diversity scores are 29.8 for Gemini, 16.4 for GPT, and 10.7 for Claude, underscoring clear differences among families. This figure extends the individual comparisons shown in Figure 2 by revealing broader, family-level trends that may be linked to architectural structure, training data composition, or fine-tuning strategies. Future work will assess the statistical significance of these differences and further investigate the architectural and training factors underlying them.

Figure 3: Conceptual Diversity Scores Across LLM Families

From the perspective of conceptual spaces, Gemini models appear to occupy a larger and more finely divided “conceptual hypersphere” than GPT or Claude models, which enables them to represent a broader range of divergent conceptual regions. These findings encourage further exploration of how architectural design, training corpus diversity, and fine-tuning strategies influence the geometry of a model’s conceptual space, as well as whether high diversity is associated with better performance in open-ended knowledge retrieval and reasoning tasks.

5 Discussion

The findings of this study reveal substantial differences in the diversity of conceptual regions among LLMs. The gemini-2.5-flash-preview-05-20 model achieved the highest diversity score, suggesting that it may encode a broader and more varied set of conceptual regions compared to the other evaluated models. In contrast, claude-3-7-sonnet-20250219 recorded the lowest diversity value, indicating a comparatively constrained conceptual structure according to the proposed metric. These results indicate that diversity, defined as the number of maximally divergent conceptual regions identified through prompt engineering, can serve as an indicator of a model’s capacity for factual knowledge representation. A higher diversity score may reflect a richer and more granular internal conceptual organization, which is hypothesized to enhance a model’s ability to generalize and retrieve knowledge effectively, although this relationship remains to be empirically validated. Nonetheless, diversity alone does not address the accuracy or reliability of the knowledge represented, nor does it directly assess reasoning capabilities or conceptual coherence.

The inclusion of independent models such as Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct, Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3, Gemma-3-12B-IT, and Grok-3 provides additional perspective beyond the three major families, revealing how architectural and training differences influence conceptual diversity across both family and individual model levels.

The study also highlights the value of prompt engineering as a tool for probing and exploring the latent conceptual spaces of LLMs. However, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, defining maximally divergent conceptual regions in purely conceptual terms is inherently subjective and relies on the specific formulation of prompts. Second, model outputs can vary due to sensitivity to prompt wording, which introduces measurement variability. Third, diversity measures offer only a partial view of internal knowledge structures and should be interpreted together with other evaluation approaches, such as task-based benchmarks and human-aligned assessments, in order to achieve a comprehensive understanding of model capabilities.

A closer analysis of the results indicates that variations in conceptual divergence are likely associated with differences in model architecture and training methodology. Although these factors were not explicitly examined in this study, it is plausible that design choices and training approaches influence how conceptual regions emerge and differentiate within the latent space. Fine-tuning techniques, including instruction tuning and reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF), may further refine representational granularity by aligning internal structures with human evaluation patterns. Architectural elements such as attention mechanisms, context length, and normalization procedures could also affect a model's ability to form distinct conceptual boundaries. While the present work does not establish causal relationships, the comparative results suggest that architectural and methodological variations may play an important role in shaping conceptual diversity. Future studies should investigate these aspects in greater depth to better understand how specific design configurations contribute to higher conceptual divergence.

Future research can address these limitations by refining prompt design to minimize ambiguity, incorporating human validation to confirm the identified conceptual regions, and investigating the relationship between conceptual diversity and performance on real-world tasks. In addition, combining geometric analysis with probabilistic and mechanistic interpretability frameworks may provide a more complete and robust characterization of LLM knowledge structures.

6 Conclusion

This study introduced a novel prompt engineering-based method for probing the latent conceptual spaces of LLMs by identifying maximally divergent conceptual regions. By defining and measuring the diversity of these regions, the approach provides a geometric perspective on the internal organization of knowledge in LLMs. The empirical evaluation showed notable variation in diversity scores across models, suggesting differences in their capacity to represent factual knowledge and conceptual structures.

The findings indicate that diversity, as measured through this prompt-based method, can serve as a complementary indicator of model capacity alongside established benchmarks. Although promising, the relationship between diversity and real-world performance still requires further validation. Moreover, limitations such as sensitivity to prompt phrasing and the inherent subjectivity in defining maximally divergent conceptual regions point to the need for methodological refinement.

Future research should focus on reducing variability caused by prompt design, incorporating human validation of the identified conceptual regions, and exploring the

relationship between diversity scores and performance on practical tasks. Combining this geometric analysis with other interpretability frameworks, including probabilistic modelling and mechanistic interpretability, may lead to more transparent, reliable, and comprehensive evaluations of the conceptual structures and factual knowledge capacity of LLMs.

Data Availability Statement

The data underpinning the analysis reported in this paper are deposited at “Data repository” Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17548139>.

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